

Our project at a glance

12
Partners

7
Countries

3
Years

3.97M€
EU funding

Bet everything on green!

We believe in the potential of **renewable energies** as a way to decarbonise our economy. That's why our goal at ASTERISK is to **produce hydrogen using only clean energy sources**, such as wind turbines or solar power.

Wind power

Solar power

Seawater is the key

Instead of using fresh water, a valuable resource we must preserve for other applications, we will produce green hydrogen **directly from seawater**.

Agriculture

Human consumption

Farms

TRANSFORMING SEAWATER INTO GREEN HYDROGEN

What we do

Catalysts & membranes

At ASTERISK we seek to apply **environmental consciousness** to every part of our process. Therefore, our electrolyser components will use abundant materials such as iron and nickel and avoid the use of toxic compounds, such as PFAS, also called **'forever chemicals'**.

Brine valorisation

In addition to obtaining green hydrogen, we will recover industrially valuable compounds from seawater, such as **mineral salts**. This is what we call closing the loop!

Sustainability

For us, it is important to design a device with the lowest possible environmental impact. That is why we consider the **recyclability** of all our components and different end-of-life scenarios for our electrolyser.

Our main objective: an electrolyser ready for harsh salinity conditions.

Proof of concept (PoC) of a 5 kWe stack by using seawater with degradation rate of <5% over 500h of operation

Splitting water with electricity

Although there are several methods for obtaining hydrogen, the simplest, most efficient and environmentally friendly is **water electrolysis**. This process uses electricity to separate water molecules into its components, oxygen and hydrogen.

The support behind ASTERISK

ASTERISK has ambitious goals. Fortunately, we count on funding from the **European Commission** and the **Clean Hydrogen Partnership**, which supports research and innovation on hydrogen and fuel cell technologies, to stimulate the production, distribution, storage and end-use applications of clean hydrogen.

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